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Review Paper

Analytical Method Development and Validation for the Simultaneous Estimation of Dutasteride and Tamsulosin Hydrochloride in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage forms by RP-HPLC Method

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ABSTRACT

A rapid, sensitive and precise reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed for the simultaneous quantification of Dutasteride and Tamsulosin Hydrochloride using a Waters HPLC system. Chromatographic separation was achieved on a Inertsil ODS C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size) maintained at ambient temperature. The mobile phase consisted of acetonitrile and buffer in the ratio of 80:20(v/v), which was filtered through a 0.45 μm membrane filter prior to use. The flow rate was maintained at 1.0 mL/min and detection was carried out at 228 nm using PDA detector.

INTRODUCTION

Urimax® is a combination drug containing Dutasteride and Tamsulosin hydrochloride. Dutasteride (7-8) is a synthetic 4-azasteroid compound that selectively inhibits both the type I and type II isoforms of steroid 5α-reductase, an intracellular enzyme that converts testosterone to 5α-dihydrotestosterone (DHT). Dutasteride works by reducing the levels of circulating DHT.

Tamsulosin (9-10) is a blocker of alpha-1A and alpha-1D adrenoceptors. About 70% of the alpha-1 adrenoceptors in the prostate are of the alpha-1A

subtype. By blocking these adrenoceptors, smooth muscle in the prostate is relaxed and urinary flow is improved. The blocking of alpha-1D adrenoceptors relaxes the detrusor muscles of the bladder which prevents storage symptoms. The specificity of tamsulosin from the dutasteride focuses the effects to the target area while minimizing effects in other areas. So the combination of both was shown to reduce the size of the prostate gland, improve urinary flow, and symptoms of benign prostatic hyperplasia.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

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Preparation of Stock solution: 10 mg of Tamsulosin Hydrochloride and 10 mg of Dutasteride API standards were accurately weighed and are transferred into two separate 10 ml volumetric flasks and dissolved in 10ml of mobile phase. The mixture was then sonicated for 20 minutes to obtain 1000 μ g/ml.

Preparation of working standard solution: From the stock solutions of both standards, each 0.4 ml was pipetted out and transferred in to 10ml volumetric flasks, made up to 10 ml with mobile phase and sonicated for 10 minutes, to obtain 40 μ g/ml Tamsulosin Hydrochloride and Dutasteride.

Preparation of buffer: 2.7218 gms of potassium dihydrogen phosphate was accurately weighed, transferred into 1000ml beaker and dissolved with HPLC grade water. The pH of the solution was maintained at 3.4 using orthophosphoric acid.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method validation: Validation parameters include specificity, linearity, range, accuracy, precision, limit of detection, limit of quantification, robustness and assay (1-6).

Specificity: Specificity is the ability to assessing equivocally the analyte in the presence of components which may be expected to be present. Typically, these components include impurities, degradants, matrix etc. Blank solution and standard solutions of Dutasteride (40 μ g/ml) and Tamsulosin HCl. (40 μ g/ ml) were injected into the HPLC system. The peak purity data of Dutasteride and Tamsulosin Hcl. were compared. There should not be any interference at the retention time of the main peaks (11-19).

Linearity: Linearity for the drugs Dutasteride and Tamsulosin HCl. was determined by preparing the

standard solutions at six concentrations levels in six replicates in the range of 20-70 μ g/ml Dutasteride and 20-70 μ g/ml for and Tamsulosin hydrochloride from stock solution. The linearity charts of Dutasteride and Tamsulosin HCl. was shown in the figure no 2&3. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.9996 and 0.9994 for Dutasteride and Tamsulosin Hydrochloride respectively. Linearity results were tabulated in table 2.

Accuracy: Accuracy was performed by spiking known amounts of standard solution to sample solution at three different concentrations levels (50%, 100%, 150%) and there by analyzed for %RSD which should not be more than 2.0. The % recovery was calculated and the results was reported in table no. 3 & 4.

Precision: The precision of the analytical method was studied by injecting six replicates of standard containing 40 μ g/ml of Dutasteride and 40 μ g/ml of Tamsulosin Hydrochloride which were injected into HPLC system. The % RSD was calculated and the results were reported in the table no.5 & 6.

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ): The limit of detection was defined as the concentration which yields a signal - to - noise ratio 3:1 whereas the limit of quantification was calculated to be the lowest concentration that could be measured with signal - to - noise ratio 10:1. LOD and LOQ were calculated from slope and standard deviation. The results were tabulated in table no. 7.

Robustness: The smallest deliberate changes in method like change in flow rate are made but there were no predictable changes in the results and are in the range as per ICH guidelines. Conditions like decrease in flow rate (0.8 ml/min), increase in flow rate (1.2 ml/min) was maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System

suitability parameters were not much affected and all the parameters were passed. % RSD was found to be within the limits and results were tabulated in table no. 8.

Assay: Assay was conducted on marketed formulation and mean % assay was found. The results were tabulated in table no. 9.

Table1: Optimised Chromatographic Conditions

Parameter	Method
Stationary Phase (column)	Inertsil -ODS C18 (250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile : Buffer (80:20)
Flow rate (ml/min)	1.0 ml/min
Run time (minutes)	10 min
Temperature in the column (°C)	Ambient
Injection volume (μl)	20
Detection wavelength (nm)	228nm
Drug RT (min)	4.097min for Dutasteride and 5.739 for Tamsulosin Hydrochloride.

Figure 1: Optimised Chromatogram

Table 2: Linearity data of Dutasteride and Tamsulosin Hydrochloride

Dutasteride		Tamsulosin Hydrochloride	
Conc (μg/ml)	Peak area	Conc (μg/ml)	Peak area
20	1321355	20	1038692
30	1906818	30	1596469
40	2543397	40	2129201
50	3175164	50	2733584
60	3763802	60	3302810
70	4359105	70	3785267

Figure 2: Calibration curve of Dutasteride

Figure 3: Calibration curve of Tamsulosin Hydrochloride

Table 3: Accuracy Data of Dutasteride

Concentration % of spiked level	Amount added (ppm)	Amount found (ppm)	% Recovery	Statistical Analysis of % Recovery	
				MEAN	%RSD
50% - 1	20	20.15	100.75	99.68	
50% - 2	20	19.86	99.31		
50% - 3	20	19.80	99.02		0.92
100 % - 1	40	39.88	99.70	99.841	
100 % - 2	40	40.12	100.30		
100% - 3	40	39.80	99.50		0.41
150% - 1	60	60.12	100.21	99.984	
150% - 2	60	59.76	99.61		
150% - 3	60	60.06	100.10		0.31

Table 4: Accuracy Data for Tamsulosin Hydrochloride

Concentration % of spiked level	Amount added (ppm)	Amount found (ppm)	% Recovery	Statistical Analysis of % Recovery	
				MEAN	%RSD
50% - 1	20	19.95	99.75	99.55	
50% - 2	20	20.14	100.7		
50% - 3	20	19.64	98.2		1.26
100 % - 1	40	39.95	99.87	100.08	
100 % - 2	40	40.12	100.3		
100% - 3	40	40.03	100.07		0.215
150% - 1	60	59.84	99.73	100.45	
150% - 2	60	60.84	101.40		
150% - 3	60	60.14	100.23		0.85

Table 5: System Precision data of Dutasteride and Tamsulosin Hydrochloride

Sr. No	Dutasteride	Tamsulosin Hydrochloride
1	2543124	2127335
2	2542791	2128342
3	2543018	2129324
4	2536270	2129877
5	2534021	2129856
Mean	2539845	2128947
SD	4364.582	1095.203
% RSD	0.171844	0.051443

Table 6: Method Precision data of Dutasteride and Tamsulosin Hydrochloride

Sr. No	Dutasteride	Tamsulosin Hydrochloride
1	2543206	2128756
2	2543024	2138677
3	2543108	2139586
4	2542750	2146874
5	2543186	2148865
6	2543055	2149576
Mean	2543055	2142056
SD	165.3825	8006.679
% RSD	0.0065033	0.373785

Table 7: LOD and LOQ data of Dutasteride and Tamsulosin Hydrochloride

Drug Name	LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Dutasteride	0.57	1.72
Tamsulosin Hydrochloride	0.16	0.49

Table 8: Robustness data of Dutasteride and Tamsulosin Hydrochloride

Sr No	Drug Name	Condition	Peak area	% RSD
1	Dutasteride	Decreased Flow rate of 0.8 ml/min	2536741	0.106
2		Increased Flow rate of 1.2 ml/min	2553397	0.113
3	Tamsulosin Hydrochloride	Decreased Flow rate of 0.8 ml/min	2134045	0.184
4		Increased Flow rate of 1.2 ml/min	2157001	0.169

Table 9: Assay data Dutasteride and Tamsulosin Hydrochloride

Sr. No	Peak area of Dutasteride	% Assay	Peak area of Tamsulosin Hydrochloride	% Assay
1	2543124	100.504	2127335	98.49
2	2542791		2128342	
3	2543018		2129324	
4	2536270		2129877	
5	2534021		2129856	

CONCLUSION

The developed RP-HPLC method was validated as per ICH guidelines. All the system suitability parameters were within the range as stated by ICH guidelines. Interference peaks were not observed in blank, standard and sample chromatogram. Hence simple, precise and accurate, sensitive, specific and robust method was developed and validated. This can be used in quality control department with respect to routine analysis.

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